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Abstract

The article analyzes the theoretical foundations of improving strategic planning and corporate governance systems, international experience, and their mutual integration. It also examines scientific approaches and practical mechanisms aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of modern corporate governance. As a result of the study, it is substantiated that the harmony between strategic planning and corporate governance is a key factor in increasing the competitiveness of organizations.

Keywords: strategic planning, corporate governance, efficiency, competitiveness, institutional approach, stakeholders.

Introduction

In the conditions of the modern economy, the activities of enterprises are determined by a complex and constantly changing external environment. Global competition, digital transformation, and the volatility of investment flows require a reconsideration of strategic management systems. Strategic planning is the process of defining an organization's long-term goals and developing ways to achieve them, while corporate governance is considered an institutional mechanism regulating relations among stakeholders.

At present, the efficiency of enterprises in the global economy is directly connected with the quality of strategic management and corporate governance systems. Under conditions of digital transformation, increasing market competition, and the growing complexity of the investment environment, improving strategic planning systems has become an objective necessity.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of corporate governance and strategic planning systems is also regarded as one of the priority directions of state policy. In particular, the "Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" outlines tasks related to the modernization of the economy, transformation of state-owned enterprises, and implementation of modern standards of corporate governance¹;

The Law "On Joint-Stock Companies and Protection of Shareholders' Rights" establishes the principles of transparency, accountability, and responsibility in corporate governance²;

The Presidential Decrees on the reform of state-owned enterprises for 2021–2026 set the tasks of intro-

ducing strategic management, establishing KPI systems, and aligning corporate governance with OECD standards³;

The "Corporate Governance Code" defines that the activities of the Board of Directors, the risk management system, and internal audit should be organized in accordance with international standards⁴. In addition, special attention is being paid to the implementation of international principles of corporate governance in order to improve the investment climate and increase the share of the private sector in the country. Under these conditions, the scientific analysis of the interrelationship between strategic planning and corporate governance, as well as enhancing the competitiveness of enterprises through their integration, is considered an important and relevant task.

Theoretical aspects of research.

In the scientific literature, various approaches have been developed regarding strategic planning and corporate governance. The views of different authors interpret the essence, role, and place of these two concepts in organizational activities in different ways.

H. Igor Ansoff views strategic planning as a tool for adapting enterprises to the external environment and defining directions for growth. According to him, strategy is formed based on market opportunities and product diversification⁵. Michael Porter interprets strategy as a mechanism for creating competitive advantage. He links a firm's success to the competitive forces within an industry and emphasizes that an effective strategy can be achieved through cost leadership or differentiation⁶. Michael Jensen, in his modern research, revisits agency theory and emphasizes that a focus on short-term profits in corporate governance may reduce a company's value. He highlights the need to

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy 'Uzbekistan - 2030'" dated September 11, 2023, No. UP-158. (Lex UZ - "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy).

² Corporate Governance Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the minutes of the meeting of the Commission on improving the efficiency of joint-stock companies and enhancing the corporate governance system dated December 31, 2015, No. 9.

³ G20/OECD Principles of Corporate Governance, adopted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development in 2023 (OECD Principles of Corporate Governance).

⁴ Corporate Governance Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the minutes of the meeting of the Commission on improving the efficiency of joint-stock companies and enhancing the corporate governance system dated December 31, 2015, No. 9.

⁵ H. I Ansoff. *Corporate Strategy*. McGraw-Hill. 1965, <https://archive.org/details/corporatestrateg0000anso>

⁶ M. E. Porter *Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analyzing Industries and Competitors*. Free Press, 1980.

strengthen long-term value-based management models⁷.

Authors Joseph Bower and Lynn Paine (Harvard Business School) argue that corporate governance should shift from a “compliance-based model” to a “purpose-driven governance” model. According to them, companies should be accountable not only to shareholders but also to society at large⁸. Colin Mayer emphasizes that the main purpose of corporate governance is not “profit maximization,” but “creating long-term value for society.” He argues that the social mission of companies should be at the center of strategic planning⁹.

Lucian Bebchuk advocates for strengthening shareholder control in corporate governance. He emphasizes that the compensation system should be reformed in order to reduce conflicts between managers and shareholders¹⁰. Robert Kaplan emphasizes the need to integrate the Balanced Scorecard system with ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) indicators. In his view, strategy should no longer be focused solely on financial performance, but should also be oriented toward sustainability¹¹. David Norton emphasizes that digital monitoring and real-time KPI systems are crucial for strategy implementation. He notes that strategic planning has become a dynamic process¹². Klaus Schwab, in the context of the “Fourth Industrial Revolution,” emphasizes that corporate governance must be restructured based on digital technologies, artificial intelligence, and data-driven decision-making¹³. Mariana Mazzucato argues that the strategies of governments and companies should be built on “mission-oriented innovation.” In other words, she emphasizes that strategy should be directed toward clearly defined missions for society¹⁴.

John Elkington emphasizes the need to integrate sustainable development into strategic planning through the “People–Planet–Profit” model¹⁵.

The analysis of both modern and classical scientific approaches shows that strategic planning and corporate governance systems have undergone significant evolution over time and are shifting from a traditional financial approach toward a multidimensional and integrated model.

Foreign experience of the research.

In global practice, issues of strategic planning and improvement of corporate governance are considered key factors in ensuring sustainable enterprise development, enhancing competitiveness, and increasing investment attractiveness. In the current conditions of globalization, digital transformation, and intensifying

market competition, leading countries of the world have accumulated significant experience in building effective systems of strategic management and corporate regulation¹⁶.

Michael Porter’s research occupies an important place in the development of strategic management theory. The scholar developed the concept of competitive advantage and the “Five Forces” framework, which enables enterprises to analyze industry structure and formulate effective development strategies. According to his approach, strategic planning should be aimed at achieving sustainable competitive advantages and long-term business performance¹⁷.

A significant contribution to the development of strategic management was made by Peter Drucker, who viewed strategic management as the process of defining an organization’s long-term goals and the rational allocation of resources. According to the scholar, the effectiveness of corporate governance directly depends on the quality of strategic planning and the organization’s ability to adapt to changes in the external environment. In countries such as the United States, Germany, Japan, and the United Kingdom, special attention is paid to ensuring management transparency, protecting shareholders’ rights, and strengthening the accountability of boards of directors. The European model of corporate governance is focused on balancing the interests of all stakeholders, including investors, employees, and society.

In international practice, the OECD Principles of Corporate Governance play an important role and are recognized as a global standard of effective corporate governance. These principles provide for the protection of shareholders’ rights, transparency of corporate activities, disclosure of information, increased accountability of governing bodies, and sustainable business development¹⁸.

Modern research shows that digitalization has a significant impact on strategic planning and corporate governance. International companies are actively implementing Big Data technologies, artificial intelligence, ERP and CRM systems, which contribute to improving the quality of managerial decision-making and the effectiveness of corporate control¹⁹.

Overall, international experience shows that effective strategic planning and a modern corporate governance system are essential conditions for ensuring sustainable economic growth of enterprises, increasing their competitiveness, and enabling successful adaptation to the conditions of the digital economy.

Analysis and results of the research.

⁷ P. Bolton, Jensen and Meckling at 50: Corporate Governance Revisited. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 2025.

⁸ J. Bower, & L. Paine The Error at the Heart of Corporate Leadership. *Harvard Business Review*, 2017.

⁹ C. Mayer Prosperity: Better Business Makes the Greater Good. Oxford University Press, 2018.

¹⁰ L. Bebchuk The Case for Increasing Shareholder Power. SSRN Paper, 2019.

¹¹ R. S. Kaplan Balanced Scorecard in the Age of ESG. *Harvard Business Review*, 2020.

¹² Norton & Kaplan, Balanced Scorecard (Harvard Business School) <https://hbr.org/1992/01/the-balanced-scorecard-measures-that-drive-performance>.

¹³ World Economic Forum – Fourth Industrial Revolution (<https://www.weforum.org/publications/the-fourth-industrial-revolution-by-klaus-schwab/>).

¹⁴UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/public-purpose/people/professor-mariana-mazzucato>.

¹⁵ <https://www.johnelkington.com/archive/publications/>.

¹⁶ OECD Principles of Corporate Governance 2004.

¹⁷ The Five Competitive Forces That Shape Strategy – Michael Porter.

¹⁸ Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analyzing Industries and Competitors.

¹⁹ G20/OECD Principles of Corporate Governance 2023.

During the research, the interrelationship between strategic planning and corporate governance systems was analyzed from both theoretical and practical perspectives. Based on scientific sources and international experience, it was found that the efficiency of modern enterprises is directly linked to the quality of strategic management and the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms.

The analysis showed that in classical approaches, strategic planning was mainly focused on financial outcomes, whereas in modern concepts, greater emphasis is placed on sustainable development, ESG principles, stakeholder interests, and digital transformation. In particular, the views of scholars such as Michael Porter, Peter Drucker, Robert Kaplan, and Klaus Schwab demonstrate that strategic management has evolved toward an innovative and integrated model.

The analysis of international experience revealed that in countries such as the United States, Germany, Japan, and the United Kingdom, corporate governance systems have developed based on transparency, accountability, risk management, and the effectiveness of board of directors' activities. The OECD Principles of Corporate Governance are widely applied as an international standard in corporate management. Furthermore, the study found that digital technologies Big Data, artificial intelligence, ERP, and CRM systems significantly improve strategic planning processes. Modern enterprises increasingly use real-time KPI monitoring and data-driven management systems in strategic decision-making.

The analysis of Uzbekistan's experience shows that extensive reforms are being implemented to develop corporate governance systems in line with international standards, transform state-owned enterprises, and introduce modern strategic management mechanisms. In particular, the "Corporate Governance Code," OECD standards, and the Development Strategy until 2030 form the institutional basis of this process.

The research led to the following scientific and practical results:

Strategic planning and corporate governance systems, when integrated, ensure the long-term competitiveness of enterprises.

In modern corporate governance systems, not only financial performance but also social responsibility, environmental sustainability, and stakeholder interests are considered key factors.

It has been established that the OECD Principles of Corporate Governance contribute to increasing transparency, accountability, and investor confidence in enterprises.

The integration of Balanced Scorecard, ESG indicators, and KPI monitoring systems helps improve the effectiveness of strategic management.

Digital transformation has led strategic planning to become a dynamic model, enabling faster and more accurate managerial decision-making.

Reforms implemented in Uzbekistan to modernize the corporate governance system serve as an important institutional basis for forming a governance model aligned with international standards.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, improving strategic planning and corporate governance systems is an essential condition for the development of modern enterprises. Transformational processes occurring in the global economy require organizations to adopt flexible, innovative, and sustainable management systems.

The results of the study show that the integration of strategic planning and corporate governance significantly increases enterprises' economic efficiency, investment attractiveness, and competitiveness in international markets. At the same time, the integration of digital technologies into management systems is a key factor in improving the quality of strategic decisions and ensuring business sustainability.

In the future, it is advisable to further develop corporate governance systems by widely implementing ESG principles, artificial intelligence technologies, risk management tools, and governance mechanisms based on stakeholder interests.

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